

A Simple Extractive Colourimetric Determination of Procyclidine Hydrochloride from Pharmaceutical Preparation using Food Colours

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A simple colorimetric method for the estimation of procyclidine hydrochloride from its pharmaceutical formulations is described. The method is based on the formation of coloured complexes by the drug with reagents, like sunset yellow, Carmoisine-S and Fast Red-E in acidic medium. The coloured ion-pair complexes formed are quantitatively extracted under the experimental conditions. The method is statistically evaluated and is found to be precise and accurate.

PROCYCLIDINE hydrochloride is a parasympatholytic drug used in the treatment of the Parkinsonian syndrome. The B.P.¹ describes a non-aqueous titration method for the drug with perchloric acid as the titrant and crystal violet as the indicator. The U.S.P.² also describes a non-aqueous titration method but the end-point is determined potentiometrically.

For the determination of procyclidine hydrochloride from tablets, the B.P.³ describes a volumetric method, using sodium dodecyl sulphate as titrant and dimethyl yellow-orange blue-B as the indicator. In the U.S.P.⁴, an extractive colourimetric method is described. The drug from the tablet is reacted with bromocresol purple in acetic acid solution to form a complex, which is extracted with chloroform. The absorbance is read at 405 nm. In the literature, gc⁵, ir⁶ and uv⁷ spectrophotometric and extractive colorimetric⁸ methods are described for the determination of procyclidine hydrochloride.

In the present communication, an extractive colourimetric method for the determination of procyclidine hydrochloride using food colours is described for the first time.

Experimental

Solutions of reagents were prepared in distilled water (w/v): Fast Red-E (2.0%), Carmoisine-S (0.2%) and Sunset yellow (0.5%). Potassium biphthalate buffer solution of pH 3 was prepared in distilled water for Fast Red-E and Sunset yellow. Potassium chloride-HCl buffer solution of pH 1 was prepared in distilled water for Carmoisine-S. Working standard solutions of procyclidine hydrochloride

were prepared: in case of (i) Fast Red-E, 10 mg drug diluted to 100 ml (*i.e.* 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), (ii) Carmoisine-S, 20 mg drug diluted to 100 ml (*i.e.* 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and (iii) Sunset Yellow 10 mg drug diluted to 250 ml (*i.e.* 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

Sample solution: Twenty tablets of procyclidine hydrochloride after determining the average weight were powdered. Powder equivalent to the strength of the standard procyclidine hydrochloride solution was weighed and dissolved in distilled water and diluted upto the mark.

A Spekol CZ spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells was used.

Procedure: Appropriate amount of the standard drug solution was pipetted out into a series of separating funnels. To each flask, buffer and dye solutions were added as mentioned in Table I. 10 ml chloroform (A.R.) was added to each funnel, and in the case of Carmoisine-S, 25 ml was used. The solutions were shaken for thorough mixing of the two phases and allowed to stand for a clear separation of the layers. The absorbance value of the chloroform layer was measured against the reagent blank at λ_{max} . A graph of the absorbance values against the corresponding concentration of procyclidine hydrochloride ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was plotted. The sample solution was treated in a similar manner and the absorbance values measured. The amount of the drug present in the sample was computed from the calibration graph.

To study the recovery and accuracy of the proposed method for the determination of procyclidine hydrochloride a statistical study was done. A

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED METHOD FOR PROCYCLIDINE HYDROCHLORIDE

Sl. no.	Reagent (10 ml)	Amount of drug soln. prepared $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	pH of buffer soln. (5.0 ml)	λ_{max} nm	Beer's law range $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^{-3}$ $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Stated amount of procyclidine HCl per tablet mg/tab.	Recovery %	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation %
1.	Fast Red-E	100	3.0	517	5-20	12.9	5.0	99.72	0.09	0.73
							2.5	100.83	0.08	0.61
2.	Carmoi sine-S	200	1.0	520	8-24	8.9	5.0	98.67	0.21	1.72
							2.5	101.72	0.15	1.22
3.	Sunset Yellow	40	3.0	485	4-20	12.9	5.0	102.95	0.14	1.65
							2.5	102.35	0.12	1.40

fixed volume of the sample solution was taken and three different volumes of the standard drug solution were added. Each level was carried out seven times. The total amount of the drug present in the sample was determined by the proposed method. The percentage recovery was calculated by the equation :

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{N(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \times 100$$

where, X=amount of drug added and Y=amount of the drug found per ml of the sample, and N=total number of observations.

The amount of the drug per ml of the sample by the proposed method was plotted against the amount of the drug added. The intercept represents the amount of drug per ml of the sample.

Stability study of procyclidine hydrochloride tablets by the proposed method: Accelerated stability study of the tablets were carried out by keeping the tablets in their packing at 50° for a period of 3 months (the three months period at 50° being equivalent to the condition of tablets at 2 years shelf-life). The samples from the pack were drawn at 1, 2, and 3 month period and its assay carried out by the proposed method.

It was observed that the procyclidine hydrochloride content in the tablet remained nearly constant, thus indicating that the product is stable for 2 years on shelf that has been studied. The results are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The proposed method is simple, fast and accurate. It does not suffer any interference due to common excipients, like starch, talc, etc. The values of molar absorptivity obtained indicate that the reagents used are sensitive. The B.P.^{1,2} and U.S.P.³ methods require large quantities of the drug as compared to the proposed method, where relatively small quantities are used. The values of percentage recovery are within the pharmacopoeial limits. The values of standard deviation and

coefficient of variations are low indicating high accuracy and reproducibility of the method.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF STABILITY STUDY OF PROCYCLIDINE HYDROCHLORIDE BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sl. no.	Months kept at 50°	Reagent	Stated amount of procyclidine HCl per tablet mg/tab.	Amount of drug found by the proposed method %
1.	1	Fast Red-E	5.0	100.66
	2			99.56
	3			98.14
2.	1	Fast Red-E	2.5	101.00
	2			99.80
	3			99.20
3.	1	Carmoisine-S	5.0	100.00
	2			99.62
	3			98.37
4.	1	Carmoisine-S	2.5	100.00
	2			98.75
	3			98.00
5.	1	Sunset Yellow	5.0	102.50
	2			102.50
	3			102.25
6.	1	Sunset Yellow	2.5	102.17
	2			102.20
	3			102.17

It is relatively more convenient to measure absorbance values at 515 to 520 nm on a spectrophotometer. This is because in the case of many yellow coloured ion-pair complexes the absorbance extends into the far-uv region and the exact determination of λ_{max} on a spectrophotometer becomes difficult. Again, the reagent blank in many cases have considerable absorbance in the region 410 nm and hence the absorbance have to be read at a slightly higher wave length than the λ_{max} . From this point of view, dyes reported here have a definite advantage over the bromocresol purple reported in the U.S.P.⁴ method.

The colour of the complex obtained is very stable, over a period of 30 min and hence the method is practicable for routine analytical purpose and for studying the stability of the product.

The drug-dye complex was separated. From the ir and nmr studies we propose the reaction mechanism as shown

Hence, a strong recommendation is made for the proposed method in the determination of procyclidine hydrochloride from its formulation, viz. tablets.

References

1. British Pharmacopoeia, Her Majesty's Stationary Office, London, 1980, p. 370.
2. The United States Pharmacopoeia, XX, Mack Publishing Co., Easton, 1980, p. 665.
3. British Pharmacopoeia, Her Majesty's Stationary Office, London, 1980, p. 812.
4. The United States Pharmacopoeia, XX, Mack Publishing Co., Easton, 1980, p. 666.
5. A. W. MISSEN, S. J. DICKSON and W. T. Cleary, *J. Anal. Toxicol.*, 1978, 2, 238.
6. L. G. CHATTACH and L. A. DOAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1966, 55, 372.
7. J. KRAEMAR and J. KRAEMAROVA, *Eska Farm.*, 1966, 15, 16.
8. R. T. SANE and S. V. SAWANT, *Indian Drugs*, 1982, 19, 493.